

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D6.3 Biodiversity Data flows for the EU DTO

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
DUC	Demonstrator Use Case
EC	European Commission
EC DG MARE	EC Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EU DTO	European Union Digital Twin of the Ocean
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBF	Global Biodiversity Framework
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
UN	United Nations
vLab	Virtual laboratory

Keywords

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve their understanding, their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately allow to make better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data still do not find their way into repositories due to several reasons, including cultural, legal, governance issues, lack of resources, or technical barriers. In the case of technical barriers, one of the problems may arise from systems not being able to integrate the type of biodiversity data being collected or the type of biodiversity data products being produced. Various instruments and new techniques can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimise the resources to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is still at distinct stages of development.

The DTO-BioFlow project aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO, through existing data providers and data aggregators (e.g., EMODnet Biology) when possible or establishing direct data flows to this infrastructure when required. To reach this goal, the project works on different complementary Work Packages (WPs). WP2 targets the identification and creation of an inventory of so-called "sleeping" biodiversity data; WP3 develops sustained flows of multiple biodiversity data types into the DTO; WP4 uses relevant data from the other WPs to demonstrate with policy relevant use cases the benefits of including new and "sleeping" biodiversity data in an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring; and WP5 brings the data products developed in all the other WPs into the EU DTO infrastructure, ensuring that the data and tools produced are interoperable and scalable, and that the architecture is aligned with other Digital Twin Initiatives. Finally, WP6 drives community action to increase biodiversity data flows into the DTO by 2030, connecting to both biodiversity data providers to increase the flow of FAIR biodiversity data, and to potential users of the new data flows, tools and services developed by DTO-BioFlow.

Deliverable (D6.3) presents a pamphlet built to showcase the benefits and opportunities to become a biodiversity data provider. The pamphlet also includes technical and training aspects for the potential biodiversity data providers.

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1. Introduction

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO), i.e. a digital replica of ocean processes to improve our understanding of these processes, predict their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately lead to making better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data do not find their way into repositories for a variety of reasons, e.g. a technical barrier arises when existing platforms, databases and repositories are not able to accommodate for the new types of biodiversity data being produced, due to the way the platforms were originally designed. Various instruments and new observing techniques such as DNA-based observations, plankton imaging observations, passive acoustics, or biologging data, can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimize the resources used to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is at distinct stages of development and for some, the applicable procedures and guidelines are still a work in progress, subject to frequent changes as more information becomes available.

The project DTO-BioFlow aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. Work Package (WP) 3 ‘Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO’, aims to set up the general data flow towards the EU DTO, establishing the connection towards this EU infrastructure and ensuring that sustainable data flows are in place beyond the lifetime of the project. This WP will focus on biodiversity data types from different sources: (1) genomics observation networks, (2) plankton imaging observation networks, (3) fish, mammal and bird biologging networks, (4) cetacean passive acoustic observation networks, and (5) other relevant biodiversity data sources. These biodiversity data types, some of which are quite new to the scientific community, along with other relevant biodiversity data sources will contribute data for the demonstration of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring with policy relevant use cases in WP4 ‘Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases’. Ultimately, these data will flow towards the EU DTO infrastructure developed under initiatives such as the EDITO-Infra project, with WP5 ‘Integration in DTO infrastructure’ supporting this integration of marine biodiversity data into the EU DTO infrastructure. WP6 is focused on driving community action to increase Biodiversity data Flows into the DTO by 2030, connecting to both biodiversity data providers to increase the flow of FAIR biodiversity data into EMODnet and the DTO, and to potential users of the new data flows, tools and services developed by DTO-BioFlow. This interconnection among WPs is planned to build a coherent structure of data sources and use case applications.

In the context of WP6, building on the work in WP2 and WP3, and contributing to WP4 and WP5, this document presents a pamphlet created to showcase the benefits and opportunities to become a biodiversity data provider. The pamphlet also includes technical and training aspects for the potential biodiversity data providers. It is designed in a standard stapled booklet format. This pamphlet will be widely disseminated and will support the “Biodiversity Data Providers Onboarding Campaign”, to encourage and train more biodiversity data collectors to make their data FAIR and available through EMODnet and the EU DTO.

The pamphlet is designed to be an engaging output with easy to digest information, including concise text supported by visually appealing graphics and visualizations. The proposed text for the pamphlet is provided as part of this deliverable, while the branded graphical version is provided in the DTO-BioFlow website at the following (currently) private link: <https://dto-bioflow.eu/become-biodiversity-data-provider>.

2. Pamphlet's text

Contribute to Building the Digital Twin of Our Oceans: Unlock the Power of Your Biodiversity Data

Why sharing your biodiversity data matters for science, policy, and the planet.

Calling All Biodiversity Data Holders: Make your data available to the European Digital Twin of the Ocean

[European Digital Twin of the Ocean \(European DTO\)](#)

A digital twin is a digital representation of real-world entities or processes. Digital twins use real-time, and historical, data to represent the past and present, and numerical models to simulate possible future scenarios.

The development of a digital twin of the ocean and all waters is the second target of the EU Mission “Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters”; it is built on EU assets such as [Copernicus](#) satellite Earth Observation and *in situ* (non-space) data, as well as pan-European *in situ* marine environmental (bathymetry, biology, geology, physics, chemistry and seabed habitats) and human activities data from the European Marine Observation and Data Network ([EMODnet](#)). The European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) aims to model the ocean's multiple components, provide knowledge and understanding of the past and present and create trustable predictions of its future behavior. The [EDITO-Infra](#) (“EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin”) project provides the foundation for the further development of the EU Public Infrastructure backbone for the EU DTO by upgrading, combining and integrating key service components of the existing EU ocean observing, monitoring and data programmes (i.e., Copernicus Marine Service and EMODnet) into a single digital framework.

EDITO hosts the deployment of multiple DTO applications from ongoing and future digital twin projects, supporting the deployment of new generation of ocean models (e.g. via Horizon Europe underlying models for the European DTO projects) and of the Mission lighthouses projects.

The [DTO-BioFlow](#) project aims to collect, standardize and publish both “sleeping” data (i.e., data requiring further processing to become digital, and thus currently unavailable and inaccessible), as well as new biodiversity monitoring data (e.g., DNA-based observations, plankton imaging observations, passive acoustics, or biologging data), and establish semi-automated workflows for sustained data ingestion into the EU DTO. Thus, it will create essential components for a digital replica of marine biological processes, transforming new and existing data flows into evidence-based knowledge to support ecosystem conservation efforts. DTO-BioFlow is establishing [data flows](#)

for several new biodiversity data types produced using different techniques and instruments which do not yet have established dataflows to make them available in long-term data repositories.

- "Do you collect or hold biodiversity data?"
- "Are you aware of the global effort to bring biodiversity data to life?"

Marine habitats are challenging to monitor, and many biodiversity data sources remain underused. The DTO-BioFlow project is working to address this by helping you to share your data, especially the "sleeping" data. In doing so you contribute to the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

This collaboration transforms data into knowledge, advancing scientific research, supporting conservation efforts, and informing policies. Your contribution helps model ocean scenarios, strengthening global efforts to protect marine biodiversity and support the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, amongst others.

Here's how sharing your data can make a meaningful impact!

Key Benefits of Sharing Your Data

Sharing your data will:

- **Enhance the impact of your work** and increase your citation rates.
- **Add value to your data:** Combining data from multiple sources improves the quality of analyses and creates richer, more impactful data products.
- **Reduce data collection efforts:** Reducing repeated collections means less environmental impact and allows resources to be redirected to gathering new data or supporting other critical needs.
- **Support corporate social responsibility:** Sharing data contributes to the greater good.
- **Meet funder requirements:** Data collected or generated with public funding should be openly accessible.
- **Safeguard your data:** Depositing your data in a repository ensures it is protected and reduces the risk of loss.
- **Make your data FAIR:** Making your data FAIR, will make it easier for others to find and use them, and will give the data a lifetime far beyond what it could otherwise achieve.

Better data leads to better decisions. As a data provider, you retain full ownership of your data! You also control its availability and decide when it should be made publicly accessible.

Opportunities for Your Data

Visual: A flowchart or timeline showing the process from data submission to impact (data collection → open-access repositories → impact conservation and management strategies → support

authorities in monitoring activities and in fulfilling environmental reporting (e.g. Marine Strategy Framework Directive))

Publishing data (and metadata) in online, open-access repositories transform them into invaluable assets for the scientific community. These repositories and data integrators serve as vital resources for advancing knowledge and driving real-world change.

The EU DTO will bring together data from different sources (e.g., biological, environmental, etc.) into a single platform, allowing users to access the available tools and applications, as well as to develop new ones based on their own needs.

The stored data can be used to:

- **Formulate conservation strategies** for flagship and endangered species.
- **Assess the long-term impact of human-induced threats** like global warming, ocean acidification, and pollution on biodiversity.
- **Prevent future biodiversity loss and mitigate habitat fragmentation.**
- **Advance progress towards global sustainability goals**, including the UN Sustainable Development Goals, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.
- **Influence legislative frameworks and inform the development and implementation of policies** for biodiversity management and monitoring.
- **Support decision-makers and stakeholders** in making informed, scientifically sound, data-driven choices.
- **Identify critical knowledge gaps** (e.g., taxonomical or regional) to guide focused research efforts.
- **Answer a wide range of scientific questions** that contribute to the advancement of the field.

PRACTICAL USE CASES

Your data could support DTO-BioFlow's Demonstrator Use Cases!

DTO-BioFlow develops policy-relevant demonstrator use cases (DUCs) to showcase the benefit of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring. Interfaces for new data flows, models and algorithms could be integrated in the EU DTO, providing knowledge outputs to inform the protection and restoration of ecosystems and supporting progress towards EU biodiversity goals.

DUCs will build on the data collected under the EU DTO and on its workflows and virtual laboratories (vLabs), to run virtual experiments, support and enhance decision-making. Currently, there are eight conceptualized DUCs focusing on: a) invasive species management, b) impact from offshore infrastructures, c) human impact on pelagic biodiversity, d) spatial planning of sustainable

mariculture, e) ecosystem-based spatial planning and management of marine protected areas, f) lower-trophic level biomass monitoring, g) ecosystem services (including carbon sequestration), h) machine learning for ocean colour forecasting.

DTO workflows and vLabs, combined with artificial intelligence and high-performance computing, will be available to end users and data providers, so that they can integrate all the available data from all the different data sources to create their own custom data products!

You can explore the currently available applications and become a [beta tester](#) of the EDITO-infra platform!

TRAININGS

DTO-BioFlow training material will be made available on how to reformat, publish and quality control biodiversity data, while aligning them with international standards so that they can flow to (the European node of) the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (([Eur](#))OBIS) and the European Marine Observation and Data Network ([EMODnet](#)) ([Biology thematic portal](#)).

Best practices in data management will also be a part of the training material. A [slide deck](#) created for the data training workshops for the recipients of the DTO-BioFlow grants for data holders is available at the project's website.

Other training opportunities

For dedicated self-paced trainings, you can visit the Ocean Teacher Global Academy, create your account and browse through the [Biological Data Management 2024 course](#) or the [Ocean Data Management 2024 course](#) or the [Contributing datasets to EMODnet Biology](#) course.

For more detailed information, you can browse through the [online dataset submission](#) form of EurOBIS.

If you experience issues in making your data FAIR, you can find dedicated courses on the [Marine Training platform](#), such as the [FAIR DATA for marine sciences training course](#)

How to Contribute Your Data: A guide

Have we made a compelling case? Below is a step-by-step guide to submitting your data.

Step 1: Identify a suitable repository for your dataset.

For example, marine species distribution data of Europe should be submitted to EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology. A non-exhaustive list of data repositories and integrators is available on the DTO-BioFlow Blueprint, which will be publicly available in 2025.

Step 2: Format the dataset based on the proper standard.

In case of marine species distribution data, the used standard is Darwin Core.

Step 3: Submit the data!

For EurOBIS and EMODnet Biology, data submission can go through the Integrated Publishing (IPT) Toolkit or e-mail. For EMODnet, an additional option is submitting data through the [EMODnet Data Ingestion Portal](#).

EurOBIS publishes distribution data on marine species, collected within European marine waters or collected by European researchers outside European marine waters. It is an online marine biogeographic database compiling data on all living marine creatures. The principle aims of EurOBIS are to centralize the largely scattered biogeographic data on marine species collected by European institutions and to make these data freely available and easily accessible.

EMODnet is the European Commission (EC) *in situ* marine data service of the EC Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EC DG MARE) and funded by the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. Established in 2009, EMODnet plays a pivotal role as a trusted source of *in situ* marine environmental and human activities data and data products, serving a diverse user base across various sectors.

YOUR BIODIVERSITY DATA CAN MAKE THE DIFFERENCE

Biodiversity is crucial for a sustainable planet, but its rapid decline threatens ecosystems, food security, and economic stability. Tackling this issue requires global cooperation, knowledge sharing, and **data integration**.

By contributing your data to initiatives like the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean, you play an essential role in shaping informed strategies for biodiversity conservation.

Join the effort today — share your data and be part of the solution for a healthier planet.

